

INTRODUCTION

Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector Submission

Thank you for participating in the Eclipse Soundscapes (ES) Project as a Data Collector!

Participating as an Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector will support research on the effects of solar eclipses on the environment! Your submission is very important and research at this scale could not be done without your input! All recorded and submitted audio data and submitted audio data recording location information will be freely and publicly available with an attribution thanking volunteers for their contribution.

In addition to collecting data using the AudioMoth recording device and a MicroSD card, please use this form to enter information about the AudioMoth data recording location.

You will receive a certificate of completion after you submit

your audio data by mailing the MicroSD card back to the Eclipse Soundscapes (ES) team. You can find mailing instructions on the [Data Collector page](#) on the ES website.

DIRECTIONS: Complete this form after you have collected AudioData for 5 days with your AudioMoth device. To complete this form you will need:

1. Your AudioMoth's ES ID #
2. Latitude and longitude of the AudioMoth's recording location [FORMAT: Decimal degrees (DD): 41.40338, 2.17403]
3. Audio data collection start date & time and end date & time

Eclipse Soundscapes Identification number (ES ID #)

Info: If you received the AudioMoth from the ES team, the number is located on the outside of the AudioMoth box in braille and print. It is also located in print on the AudioMoth device itself in print in the bottom right corner of the device. If you did not receive your AudioMoth from the ES team you must [register your AudioMoth](#) on the ES website to receive a unique 3 digit ES ID #.

After submitting your data location information, you will be invited to participate in a survey about your

experience. Your participation is entirely voluntary. Your responses to the survey will be separated from your data collection location submission to maintain confidentiality. Results from the survey will be reported in aggregate to evaluate the program's impact and support research efforts in determining how projects like this affect people's science identity.

Open Data Policy: Please see the “[Open Data Policy](#)” page on the EclipseSoundscapes.org website for more information about this policy and where ES data will be stored.

The entire process is expected to take 10–15 minutes. If you have any questions, feel free to contact ESCSP_PI@ArisaLab.org.

What is your 5-digit zip code?

This might be different from the zip code where you completed the data collection. This information is shared with NASA Science Activation so that they can better understand where people are getting involved with the projects that they support. If you do not know your zip code,

or if you live outside of the United States, please enter 99999.

I understand that any data that I provide will be used for the stated purposes: first, to collect eclipse audio data and recording location information; second, to identify when I plan to mail my MicroSD card; and third, to help evaluate how participatory science influenced my science identity.

I understand that the Eclipse Soundscapes project is run by ARISA Lab, but a different organization called The Mark USA has been hired to collect the data that I will provide online. The Mark USA will *not* share any identifiable information that I provide (for example, my name and email address) with ARISA Lab. Also, The Mark USA will *not* use my information for any purposes beyond those stated here and will *not* share or sell my contact information or other data for any reason, unless obligated by law.

I understand that my IP address and geo-location data will not be automatically recorded. However, I understand that I will be asked to self-report my data collection location's latitude and longitude to help the Eclipse Soundscapes

Team and others know where the audio data was collected.

- I consent to providing information for the purposes of this study. I understand that I can opt out at any time by closing the tab or window.**

LOCATION

What is the location of your data collection? Please enter your location using your device's location or type in latitude and longitude in decimal degrees. (Example: 41.40338, 2.17403)

Latitude

Longitude

Please select the option that describes your outside data collection location:

- Urban / City
- Suburban
- Rural / Countryside

Please select additional descriptions that describe your outside data collection location: Choose all that apply.

- Park
- Forest
- Field or pasture
- Desert
- Beach
- Riverfront
- Lakefront
- Mountain area
- Hiking or Biking trail
- Zoo
- Farm
- National Park, please specify:
- National or State Forest, please specify:
- Other, please specify:

Do you have additional information to share about your location? (For example, near a major road? Near

**a power generator or power supply station? Near particular animals/insects nesting/habitat? etc)
Details and info always help!**

What dates did you start and end audio data collection? Use the following format: YYYY/MM/DD

Start Date

End Date

Data Collection Start Time:

What time did you begin your data collection? Please include the hour and minute separated by a colon (HH:MM format), using a 24-hour clock. Valid examples include 08:32 and 20:09.

Data Collection Stop Time:

What time are you stopping your data collection? Please include the hour and minute separated by a colon (HH:MM format), using a 24-hour clock. Valid examples include 08:32 and 20:09.

Please select your time zone:

- Eastern Time Zone
- Central Time Zone
- Mountain Time Zone
- Pacific Time Zone
- Alaska Time Zone
- Hawaii-Aleutian Time Zone

What is your AudioMoth's 3 digit ES ID#?

SUBMISSION

Directions: Please follow the instructions below to submit your audio data.

Audio Data Submission Instructions: In a padded envelope, please mail your MicroSD card to:

ES Team c/o ARISA Lab
47 High Street Ste 501
Medford, MA 02155

Please include a piece of paper with the following information:

- ES ID#
- Latitude/longitude of data recording location

The Eclipse Soundscapes Team is NOT able to return MicroSD cards to volunteers.

When will you mail your MicroSD Card?

Use this format - MM/DD/YYYY

Thank you, we will check in with you via email each week to confirm you have mailed your data. Once you've mailed your MicroSD to the ES team, you will receive a Data Collector Certificate via email.

Any questions, please contact info@EclipseSoundscapes.org.

Please provide your email address so we can check in with you on the MicroSD mailing and then email you a Data Collector Certificate.

The evaluation team would like to interview some ES Project participants to learn more about their

experiences. Do we have your permission to contact you in the future to request an interview?

- Yes
- No, thank you

Would you like your SciStarter account to be credited for your participation?

- Yes
- No

Please enter the email address associated with your SciStarter account.

EXPERIENCE

Please indicate how much you agree with the following statements regarding your experience of the eclipse.

Strongly Disagree Moderately Disagree Somewhat Disagree Neutral Somewhat Agree Moderately Agree Strongly Agree

I experienced the passage of time differently.

I had the sense of being connected to everything.

I experienced something greater than myself.

I felt challenged to understand the experience.

***BEFORE* being an Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector, which of the following senses did you think you should use to make scientific observations? Choose all that apply.**

- Eyes / Sight
- Ears / Sound

- Touch / Feel
- Nose / Smell
- Tongue / Taste

Now, *AFTER* being an Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector, which of the following senses did you think you should use to make scientific observations? Choose all that apply.

- Eyes / Sight
- Ears / Sound
- Touch / Feel
- Nose / Smell
- Tongue / Taste